

Copyright and AI Consultation

Response from BRAID and Ada Lovelace Institute

We write in response to the government's Consultation on Copyright and Artificial Intelligence. This joint response represents the views of the Ada Lovelace Institute, a UK-based independent research institute with a mission to ensure data and AI work for people and society, and Bridging Responsible AI Divides (BRAID), a UK-wide academic programme dedicated to integrating Arts and Humanities research more fully into the responsible AI ecosystem, as well as bridging the divides between academic, industry, policy and regulatory work on responsible AI.

While we hold several concerns with the government's proposed response, we draw particular attention to **Questions 1 and 2, and Question 45**. We draw particularly on evidence from a November 2024 expert workshop exploring data deals between major news publishers and US AI labs, that brought together news publishers, AI and natural language processing experts, lawyers, legal scholars and copyright experts. In this workshop, we sought to understand the challenges that news publishers are facing under the current regime of data sharing contracts with major AI companies. As a result of this workshop, we are concerned with the government's proposed course of action in this consultation (Option 3) and suggest they move forward with Option 1.

Questions 1 and 2

In response to Question 1 (Do you agree that Option 3 is most likely to meet the objectives set out above?) and Question 2 (Which option do you prefer and why?), we believe the position of the government **should be a regime like Option 1** that would strengthen copyright law to require licensing in most cases.

Option 3 provides a broad data-mining exemption that would entail:

- AI developers being allowed to train their models for any purpose on copyrighted content that they have lawful access to. It would only apply where the rights holder has not explicitly reserved their rights.

- Rights holders can reserve their rights by opting out of having their content used for AI training. This would be done by a machine-readable format.
- The approach would be supported by mandatory transparency measures from AI developers about what content they use for training.

While we broadly agree with the government’s objectives of ensuring control, access and transparency over copyrighted works, **Option 3 fails to achieve these outcomes.** It relies on technical methods that either do not exist or are currently ineffective to enforce an opt-out regime for data mining, and a transparency regime that puts an impossible onus on rights holders to search for where their works may be misused.

In generative AI products and services, data from rights holders may be used during three main points of the development and deployment process:

Pre-training involves feeding AI models large datasets so they learn to recognise patterns or correlations and can then make inferences based on new inputs. For instance, when pre-training LLMs, data is split into tokens – words or parts of words – and statistical correlations are derived and encoded as vectors. The model uses these vectors to iteratively refine its representations of language, by adjusting the parameters to fit the training data until it performs well enough in the pre-training task.

Fine-tuning involves further training a pre-trained model on a smaller, targeted dataset to adapt it to suit more specialised use cases and tasks.

Inference and retrieval augmented generation (RAG): Inference is the process that a trained AI model uses to draw conclusions from new data. RAG is a technique that enables generative AI models to retrieve supporting data from information sources (e.g. knowledge bases, APIs, the web) to generate enriched responses to a user’s prompt and provide a source citation.

Across each of the three ways that data can be used in the generative AI lifecycle, there is no established machine-readable method for identifying if rights holders have

expressly reserved their rights. Attempts to enforce these for web crawling (e.g. robots.txt) have been unsuccessful – companies seeking to use data that is blocked by robots.txt bypass these controls regularly, and there is no meaningful way to ensure a company is compliant with these crawlers.¹ Similar methods for blocking data mining, like rate limiting by CAPTCHAs, can also be bypassed. Machine-readable rights reservations would need be captured in the metadata on a digital copyrighted work, but these metadata tags can be easily removed, even unintentionally through innocuous methods like sharing an image on social media.²

News publishers in particular have reported widespread unauthorised use of their content by AI systems for pre-training and fine-tuning AI models, with limited ability to control or even monitor such usage. This extends beyond the use of text to include unauthorised scraping of video and audio content for pre-training and fine-tuning large language models (LLMs). Publishers have found existing technical measures insufficient to prevent unauthorised data extraction for training, with evidence that many AI companies do not respect terms of service requests or robots.txt protocols.^{3,4,5}

One of the major risks of Option 3 is that it would enable large US technology companies to use a broad exemption to further cannibalise data from the UK's publishing sector. Some news organisations like the Wall Street Journal and New York Post have filed a copyright and trademark infringement lawsuit against AI start-up Perplexity. The New York Times entered negotiations with OpenAI and Microsoft, but abruptly pulled out to launch one of the most high-profile lawsuits to date, seeking damages, restitution and costs as well as the destruction of LLMs trained on its content. The lawsuits highlight how ineffective opt-out and transparency mechanisms have been to date. We are concerned that the government's proposals fail to offer a viable way to address these core issues.

Today, independent news organisations in the UK and Europe must be protected from the misuse of their copyrighted works in ways that redirect advertising revenue, reduce compensation for journalists, and undermine their reputation. The rapid development and commercialisation of generative AI, including language, image, audio and video models, has raised concerns about undesirable impacts on the news industry and broader media landscape. Core to these concerns are claims of copyright infringement for use of news content to train AI models without a license and the wider implications

¹ Ed Newton Rex. The insurmountable problems with generative AI opt-outs.

<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5cc5785816b6406e50258c5c/t/67368c12cc35b5469feb0bfd/1731628050768/The+insurmountable+problems+with+generative+AI+opt-outs.pdf>

² <https://us.norton.com/blog/how-to/how-to-remove-gps-and-other-metadata-locations-from-photos>

³ <https://www.theverge.com/2024/7/25/24205943/anthropic-ai-web-crawler-claudebot-ifixit-scraping-training-data>

⁴ <https://www.tomshardware.com/tech-industry/artificial-intelligence/several-ai-companies-said-to-be-ignoring-robots-dot-txt-exclusion-scraping-content-without-permission-report>

⁵ <https://www.theverge.com/24067997/robots-txt-ai-text-file-web-crawlers-spiders>

for intellectual property (IP) rights. Moreover, practical questions regarding the difficulty of retroactive application of transparency for developed models remain unresolved. This is particularly concerning for smaller publishers or independent journalists, who may have less ability to reserve their rights due to limited resources or capacity to establish licensing agreements.

As a result, **we believe the position of the government should be closer to Option 1, as listed in the consultation, which would strengthen copyright law to require licensing in most cases for copyrighted works.** This proposal would place the burden appropriately on large technology companies to compensate rights holders for the use of their data. The government could bolster this through the creation of a collective licensing scheme for rights holders and by ensuring that major technology companies are transparent about their uses of data.

The government might also consider including exemptions for text and data mining that relate to scientific use cases. This might steer the use of AI systems towards publicly beneficial outcomes. It is possible to train publicly beneficial AI systems using data that has been legally acquired – DeepMind’s AlphaFold protein folding model, for example, used legally acquired data to train and run a model that is now used to develop novel drugs. In deciding which option to pursue, the government must consider what may be sacrificed by providing a general text-and-data-mining exemption which requires the goodwill of large US technology companies to enforce, and which rests on hypothetical technical solutions that are not yet developed, let alone proven to be effective.

Question 45

Our evidence indicates that the current legal framework for AI products that interact with copyrighted works at the point of inference is inadequate and requires significant clarification and strengthening. Publishers also have no way to describe in detail what a crawler/scrapper can and can’t do (e.g. allowing it to search but not train on data), with initiatives such as robots.txt and firewalls only offering a binary yes/no option. While much attention has focused on training data rights, there is limited legal clarity around how copyright applies when AI systems access and use content during live inference.

This is a common feature of many generative AI products like Perplexity, ChatGPT, Google Gemini and AI Overview (Apple’s AI news alerts), and increasingly in more recent products that seek to automatically generate research outputs (e.g. OpenAI and Google’s respective Deep Research tools). These products rely on RAG and other inference-time features to pull copyrighted works from the web or proprietary databases, and to generate summaries of their original content. In doing so, they risk misattributing the original source, changing the meaning of the work in ways that harm

the rights holder's reputation, misinforming the public, and undermining the revenue model of the content's publishers.

In our November 2024 workshop with news publishers, legal scholars and AI experts, participants provided evidence of serious issues with accurate attribution and transparency in AI-generated content. Examples include:

- Cases where AI systems have generated content falsely attributed to news organisations.
- Instances of AI-generated summaries containing factual errors while citing legitimate news sources.
- Difficulties in tracing AI outputs back to specific works used in training.
- Problems with AI systems creating synthetic content that appears to come from legitimate news sources.

Specific examples included Apple's AI news alerts misrepresenting information.⁶ The BBC⁷ also produced a research report based on tests of several products, such as Perplexity, Google Gemini and Microsoft CoPilot, and found:

- 51% of all AI answers to questions about the news were judged to have significant issues of some form.
- 19% of AI answers which cited BBC content introduced factual errors – incorrect factual statements, numbers and dates.
- 13% of the quotes sourced from BBC articles were either altered from the original source or not present in the article cited.

Publishers presented evidence of direct harm to their brands and reputation when AI systems generate inaccurate content while citing them as sources. This is particularly problematic because:

- The generation happens in closed chat environments on a one-to-one basis.
- Outputs can change every time they are generated.
- Publishers cannot effectively monitor or correct misattributions or errors.
- There is no clear liability framework for harmful or incorrect AI-generated content.

The current framework provides insufficient tools for monitoring and enforcing rights during inference, particularly given the dynamic and closed nature of AI-generated inference products.

Workshop participants provided evidence of economic impacts, including:

⁶ Apple suspends error-strewn AI generated news alerts, BBC

News: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cg5ggew08eyo>

⁷ <https://www.bbc.co.uk/aboutthebbc/documents/bbc-research-into-ai-assistants.pdf>

- Reduced traffic to news websites following the introduction of AI-powered search features (5-10% drops reported by some publishers).
- Challenges in monetising content when AI systems extract and repurpose it without compensation.
- Additional costs incurred in attempting to monitor and control AI system use of a publisher's content.

Recommended framework improvements

Based on the workshop findings, we recommend the following improvements to the legal framework:

1. **Clear licensing requirements:** Establish explicit licensing requirements for both training and inference use of copyrighted works, providing certainty for both rights holders and AI developers. This may take the form of an **opt-in** regime for **inference time retrieval of online news publishing content**.
2. **Transparency obligations:** Implement mandatory requirements for AI companies to disclose not just training data but also how works are used during inference and RAG processes.
3. **Liability framework:** Develop clear guidelines on liability for AI-generated content that misattributes or misrepresents copyrighted works.
4. **Enforcement mechanisms:** Create specific enforcement mechanisms that account for the technical complexity of AI systems and the challenge of monitoring inference-time use of copyrighted works.

Conclusion

The evidence from our workshop strongly supports Option 1 of the consultation: strengthening copyright to require licensing in all cases. This approach would provide the clarity and protection needed by rights holders while establishing a stable framework for AI development. The workshop findings demonstrate that current frameworks are insufficient to address the challenges posed by AI systems, particularly regarding inference-time use of content and the emergence of synthetic data. A stronger copyright framework, supported by clear licensing requirements and robust enforcement mechanisms, would best serve the interests of both publishers and AI developers while ensuring the sustainability of quality independent news organisations.

About the Ada Lovelace Institute

The Ada Lovelace Institute is an independent research institute with a mission to ensure data and AI work for people and society.

It was established by the Nuffield Foundation in early 2018, in collaboration with The Alan Turing Institute, the Royal Society, the British Academy, the Royal Statistical Society, the Wellcome Trust, Luminate, techUK and the Nuffield Council on Bioethics.

It believes that a world where data and AI work for people and society is a world in which the opportunities, benefits and privileges generated by data and AI are justly and equitably distributed and experienced.

About BRAID

BRAID is a UK-wide programme dedicated to integrating Arts and Humanities research more fully into the Responsible AI ecosystem, as well as bridging the divides between academic, industry, policy and regulatory work on responsible AI.

It represents a six-year, £15.9 million investment in enabling responsible AI in the UK, funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) from 2022 to 2028. Grant number AH/X007146/1.

Working in partnership with the Ada Lovelace Institute and BBC, its team brings together expertise in human-computer interaction, moral philosophy, arts, design, law, social sciences, journalism, and AI. BRAID is extended by a network of interdisciplinary researchers and partnering organisations through the delivery of funding calls, community building events, and a series of programmed activities.